

Table S2. Five v. 4 gene models that may be correct without splitting

Locus ID v. 4	Original locus name	Locus ID v. 5.1.9	New locus name	Reference
Medtr7g113890	MtGSHS1	MtrunA17_Chr7g0273151	MtGSHSa	Frendo et al., 2001, 2005; Data S16 Slides 7-9 and 13
		MtrunA17_Chr7g0273161	MtGSHSb	
Medtr1g102190	MtLICK1	MtrunA17_Chr1g0204221	MtLICK1a	Wang et al., 2025b
		MtrunA17_Chr1g0204231	MtLICK1b	Wang et al., 2025b
Medtr4g088055	MtROP7	MtrunA17_Chr4g0046211	MtROP7a	Wang et al., 2021d
		MtrunA17_Chr4g0046221	MtROP7b	Wang et al., 2021d
Medtr4g073400	MtSYT1	MtrunA17_Chr4g0037111	MtSYT1a	Gavrin et al., 2017
		MtrunA17_Chr4g0037121	MtSYT1b	Gavrin et al., 2017
Medtr3g117120	NA (bZIP transcription factor)	MtrunA17_Chr3g0144931	NA (bZIP transcription factor)	Data S16 Slides 28-30
		MtrunA17_Chr3g0144941	NA (bZIP transcription factor)	Data S16 Slides 28-30

“NA” stands for “not available” (the locus has not been studied yet).